

Article

Optimizing PHEV Battery Capacity with Battery Degradation

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Abstract

Plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs) operate using both electricity and liquid fuel, offering emissions reduction while eliminating driving-range concerns. Determining the optimal electric range or battery capacity is crucial for the total cost of ownership, decarbonization potential, and battery material demand. However, the effect of battery degradation has not been incorporated into market-oriented range-optimization studies. This paper extends the existing MOR-PHEV range optimization model by integrating both cycle-based and calendar-based battery degradations. The results show meaningful optimization benefits, reducing consumer ownership cost by approximately \$3000–5000. The optimal solution—defined by the minimized lifetime cost and the optimal battery capacity—is robust across the key external parameters. Intertwined with certain factors, battery degradation can have a significant impact on the optimal battery capacity. Particularly, at faster cycle-based degradation, high driving intensity and high CS efficiency can lead to optimization tipping points, where the degradation effect is so significant that the consumer is better off by choosing a small-battery PHEV (or HEV if the choice space expands beyond PHEV) in order to fully degrade the battery faster, totally avoid the charging behavior cost earlier, and maximally benefit from the high CS efficiency earlier. This points to the importance of reducing the cycle-based degradation coefficient and improving the vehicle energy efficiency and charging convenience. One basis point (0.01%) reduction in the cycle-based degradation coefficient is estimated to reduce the optimal battery capacity by 4.9–5.2 kWh and increase consumer value by \$275–497, depending on the battery unit cost. These are useful insights into decision-making regarding battery technology R&D, battery chemistry roadmaps, critical material supply risks, and EV product strategies. While the findings in the study scope depend on assumptions of consumer behavior, battery degradation, vehicle efficiency and charging infrastructure, the expanded MOR-PHEV provides a systematic framework for considering different assumptions in support of user-defined decision context and discussing future research.

Keywords: plug-in hybrid electric vehicles; battery capacity optimization; range optimization; battery degradation; energy systems; transportation economics

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1. Introduction

Anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, primarily carbon dioxide (CO₂), disrupt the natural carbon cycle and accelerate global climate change [1]. Transportation accounts for about one quarter of global CO₂ emissions, second only to electricity and heat production [2]. As global standards of living increase and populations rise, the level of

universally desired vehicle ownership is primed to continue to increase as it has for decades. In 2024, passenger road vehicles contributed to about 45% of CO₂ emissions from the transportation sector, or about 11% of emissions globally [2]. Despite the record-high level of vehicle electrification and the temporary demand suppression by the pandemic, the total CO₂ emissions of passenger vehicles in 2023 reverted to the 2019 pre-pandemic level, due to growing income and population in some developing countries [3].

Besides greenhouse gases, many social and environmental issues of transportation are associated with the use of internal combustion engine vehicles (ICEVs) powered by gasoline or diesel, which have dominated the automotive industry for over a century. Therefore, one solution direction points to the adoption of alternative fuel vehicles. Countries and regions around the world, especially California in the United States, have explored several fuel options, such as electricity, biofuels, natural gas, liquefied petroleum gas, hydrogen, and synthetic fuels [4]. More recently, electric vehicles (EVs) such as battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs) are rapidly gaining popularity around the world, motivated by concerns over climate change, air pollution, energy security and industry growth and facilitated by battery technology breakthroughs, charging infrastructure deployment, consumer acceptance and policy support. In 2023, 40.5 million PHEVs and BEVs were in operation around the world, up from 26.3 million in 2022 and 4.9 million in 2018. EVs made up 18% of total car sales in 2023, up from 14% in 2022 and 2% in 2018 [5].

While BEVs may still face consumer concerns over range anxiety and charging infrastructure availability, PHEVs combine the convenience of ICEVs and the option of driving on electricity [6]. PHEVs have two modes: charge-depleting (CD) mode, where the vehicle is powered by the battery and electric motor with no net use of gasoline, and charge-sustaining (CS) mode, where the vehicle is powered by the combustion engine with no net use of electricity. The battery's capacity determines how much electricity can be stored and thus how far a fully charged vehicle can travel in CD mode — this is called the electric range of a PHEV. Like BEVs, which are powered solely by battery electricity, PHEVs in CD mode produce almost no direct emissions of CO₂ and other pollutants. One advantage that PHEVs have over BEVs is that once their battery is depleted, they can continue to drive by switching to CS mode. Gasoline stations are more abundant than EV recharging stations and can extend the driving range much faster than charging stations. This decreases consumers' "range anxiety" — the fear that an electric vehicle's battery capacity is not high enough to reach the destination or a recharging location — and allows for the PHEV to be operated indefinitely as long as gas stations are available. Although PHEVs in CS mode can generate direct emissions, studies have shown that if charged every day or sufficiently frequently, PHEVs can be associated with a high utility factor (i.e., share of driving distance electricity), such as 77% with a daily recharged 15 kWh battery [7]. This potentially means an ideal balance of low CO₂ emissions and range assurance.

Several strategies are being carried out to promote the adoption of BEVs and PHEVs, such as improving battery technologies, expanding charging infrastructure and providing policy incentives. In terms of vehicle design, one key strategy is to optimize the electric range (i.e., the battery capacity) in order to maximize the ownership value for targeted consumers, based on their personal circumstances such as driving patterns [8]. While range optimization for BEVs must consider range anxiety or range limitation, PHEV range optimization is mainly about the explicit and implicit costs associated with the electric range or battery capacity [9]. The electricity prices, electricity consumption rate (energy needed per unit distance), gasoline prices and gasoline consumption rate (amount of gas needed per unit distance) all influence the ownership cost of a PHEV and can affect the design of its battery capacity.

PHEV range or battery capacity optimization has been an important topic from the perspectives of informing vehicle design, understanding the dynamics of related factors, maximizing consumer value for product success and reducing social burden from battery end-of-life management [9,10]. The topic has attracted more attention for another reason—critical mineral supply and GHG emissions associated with battery production. For example, lithium demand is projected to reach 300 million tons by 2050, which is mainly due to EV development, far exceeding the projected lithium supply of 170 million tons [11]. Without range optimization to reduce battery capacity and material demand, such imbalance could have market or even political consequences. This has motivated researchers to rethink the trend of large batteries [12–14]. Additionally, the GHG emissions from battery production and resource supply (lithium, nickel, etc.) have been extensively studied and estimated to be in the range of 41 to 89 kg CO₂-eq per kWh, depending on the battery chemistry, production efficiency and carbon intensity of electricity [15,16]. For a 40-kWh battery pack, this is approximately the amount of the CO₂ emissions from driving a gasoline passenger car for 1 to 2 years (15,000 km to 30,000 km). Optimizing the PHEV electric range can promote a socially cost-effective use of battery materials and reduce the lifecycle energy, cost and GHG emissions of transportation electrification.

One key factor that is largely omitted in the PHEV range optimization literature is battery degradation. The usable capacity of a battery can decrease over time even without battery use (calendar-based degradation) or due to charge–discharge operation (cycle-based degradation) [17]. These two types of degradation are the two most overarching besides other types such as those induced by abuse, manufacturing defects, or system management. Battery degradation has been considered in a number of studies regarding the optimization of PHEV power system control [18], charging control [19], charging pattern [20] and battery pack properties [21]. For PHEV range or battery capacity optimization, battery degradation is considered in some studies that co-optimize charging strategies [22,23]. However, these studies usually assume the depth of charging as a decision variable. This approach implicitly ignores the behavior cost of a user consciously adjusting the depth of charging and is thus not very realistic. More importantly, existing studies are conducted from the perspective of automotive or electric engineers, not from the user or market perspective.

Given the importance of PHEV range optimization and the knowledge gap of battery degradation impact on the PHEV optimal range, the objective and intended contributions of this study are to (1) develop a market-oriented modeling framework that optimizes PHEV battery capacity with systematic consideration of battery degradation, (2) analyze the PHEV optimal battery capacity under the influence of battery degradation intertwined with other factors of interest, and (3) generate useful insights in support of automakers' decisions and government policies. In contrast to the existing studies on PHEV battery degradation from automotive engineering perspectives, this study takes the perspective of the consumer value and cost of ownership. Such range optimization with consideration of battery degradation aims to maximize consumer value and market adoption, rather than complying with engineering requirements.

2. Method and Data

We built on the market-oriented optimal range for the PHEV (MOR-PHEV) model framework as developed by Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, TN, the USA [9] and expanded it by adding the battery degradation mechanisms and a few other modifications. The expanded MOR-PHEV model is explained below, followed by the data and assumptions that form the base case and base alternative case studies. The results of these cases, as generated by the MOR-PHEV model, will be reported and discussed in the next section.

2.1. The Expanded MOR-PHEV Model

The decision variables (endogenous) and parameters (exogenous) to be used in the equations describing MOR-PHEV are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. MOR-PHEV model symbol notations.

Symbol	Definition	Unit	Equation #
Index			
n	index of a day during vehicle lifetime	-	3
Decision variable			
κ	battery capacity; decision variable	kWh	1
κ^*	optimal value of κ	kWh	
Parameters			
B	battery degradation due to one full charge–discharge cycle	-	4
C_0	scaling factor for the power-law cost function	-	2
C_b	pack cost at first 1 unit capacity	\$/kWh	2
C_{chg}	charging behavior cost of one recharging event	\$	7
C_{E0}	fixed coefficient for electricity consumption rate	kWh/km	3
C_{E1}	variable coefficient for electricity consumption rate	kWh/km ²	3
C_{ref}	refueling behavior cost of one refueling trip	\$	6
C_{S0}	starting coefficient for gasoline consumption rate	L/km	5
C_{S1}	ending coefficient for gasoline consumption rate	L/km	5
C_{S2}	asymptote coefficient for gasoline consumption rate	1/kWh	5
d	range extension ratio	-	3
K	calendar-based degradation coefficient	hr ^{-0.5}	4
M_n	mean of daily driving distance	km	7
M_d	mode of daily driving distance	km	7
N	assumed 3650 days based on 10 years lifetime	day	3
P_{Cs}	percentage of the battery capacity reserved for the hybrid or CS model operation	-	3
P_e	electricity price	\$/kWh	3
P_g	gasoline price	\$/L	5
Q_{fillup}	average amount of gasoline refilled each refueling trip	L	6
R	annual discount rate	-	3
Output			
D	expected daily distance traveled in CD mode	km	3
E	electricity consumption rate	kWh/km	3
f	probability density of daily driving distance	1/km	3
G	gasoline consumption rate	L/km	5
κ_n	battery capacity at the beginning of day n	kWh	
P_f	future-to-present discounting factor	-	
r	available CD range after one full charge	km	3
RC_b	one-time upfront purchase cost of the battery	\$	1
RC_c	present value (PV) of electricity charging behavior cost	\$	1
RC_e	PV of vehicle lifetime electricity cost	\$	1
RC_f	PV of gasoline refueling behavior cost	\$	1
RC_g	PV of vehicle lifetime gasoline cost	\$	1
RC_{total}	objective function; the total range-related cost	\$	1
RC_v	vehicle cost excluding battery; assumed zero because of no effect on κ^*	\$	1
S	expected daily distance traveled in CS mode	km	5

- Objective function.

The MOR-PHEV model from [9] was adopted as the starting framework as in (1).

$$\min_{\kappa} RC_{total}(\kappa) = RC_b(\kappa) + RC_e(\kappa) + RC_g(\kappa) + RC_f(\kappa) + RC_c(\kappa) + RC_v \quad (1)$$

where the objective function RC_{total} represents the total range-related cost and includes 6 linear components that are all monetized and discounted to their net present value. Battery cost RC_b is the one-time upfront purchase cost of the battery that stores electricity from the grid, the engine or the regenerative braking. Electricity cost RC_e and gasoline cost RC_g result from the use and purchase of electricity and gasoline for the PHEV operation in the CD and CS modes, respectively. The gasoline refueling behavior cost RC_f and electricity charging behavior cost RC_c represent the implicit cost of time, mental burden or annoyance associated with the refueling or recharging events, respectively. The vehicle cost RC_v refers to the costs of the vehicle, excluding the battery. All 6 components are assumed to be a function of the battery capacity κ (the decision variable), except for RC_v , which is assumed to be independent of κ for simplicity and thus can be ignored in the optimization. Importantly, the model framework in Equation (1) considers both the perceived burden and actual cost components that affect decisions, where RC_f and RC_c are perceived behavior burdens that are monetized in order to be traded off with explicit cost components.

- Battery cost.

The 1st component, $RC_b(r)$, battery cost, can be described as

$$RC_b = C_b \cdot \kappa^{C_0} \quad (2)$$

where κ represents the battery capacity for the brand-new PHEV, C_b represents the battery cost per unit capacity at $\kappa = 1$ kWh, and C_0 is the scaling factor, which is typically smaller than 1, as RC_b increases less than proportionally with κ and the battery unit cost RC_b/κ decreases with κ .

- Electricity cost.

The 2nd component, RC_e , electricity cost, can be described in Equation (3) as a function of the expected distance traveled in CD mode $D(\kappa_n)$ on day n , the electricity consumption rate $E(\kappa)$, the electricity price P_e and the future-to-present discounting factor $P_f(n)$, which is based on the annual discount rate R . The function for RC_e is based on physics and engineering economics.

$$\begin{aligned} RC_e &= \sum_{n=1}^N D(\kappa_n) \cdot E(\kappa) \cdot P_e \cdot P_f(n) \\ E(\kappa) &= C_{E0} + C_{E1} \cdot \kappa \\ D(\kappa_n) &= \int_0^{r(\kappa_n)d} xf(x)dx + r(\kappa_n)d \int_{r(\kappa_n)d}^{\infty} f(x)dx \\ r(\kappa_n) &= \frac{\kappa_n - P_{CS} \cdot \kappa}{E(\kappa)} \\ \kappa_n - P_{CS} \cdot \kappa &\geq 0 \\ P_f(n) &= (1 + R)^{\frac{-n}{365}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The CD electricity consumption rate $E(\kappa)$ is assumed to be a linear function [24] of the battery capacity κ with two parameters C_{E0} and C_{E1} , as a battery with higher capacity adds weight to the vehicle and leads to a higher electricity consumption rate. $D(\kappa_n)$ is calculated based on the available CD range $r(\kappa_n)$ at the beginning of day n after one full charge, the range extension ratio d , and the generic probability density function $f(x)$ for the random daily driving distance x , following the method in [9]. $f(x)$ is assumed to be

the Gamma distribution, proposed by [25] and validated by [26] for PHEV energy assessment, and will be discussed more in data and assumptions. $r(\kappa_n)$ is a function of κ_n , the available battery capacity at the beginning of day n , resulting from cycle- and calendar-based degradations that have been cumulated up to day n ; P_{CS} , the percentage of the battery capacity reserved for the hybrid or CS model operation; and $E(\kappa)$.

The effective electric range on day n is $r_n d$, where the range extension ratio d accounts for average daily utilization of r_n affected by within-day charger availability and charging diligence. For example, if the fully charged PHEV has an available electric range of 30 miles, is driven for 30 miles to the workplace, where the depleted battery is recharged fully, and is driven for another 30 miles in CD mode back home, then the range extension ratio is 200%, because the rated range is used 200% during that day.

The probability distribution function $f(x)$ reflects the daily driving patterns. When the daily distance x is less than the effective electric range $r_n d$, x is the distance in CD mode, and this part of $D(\kappa_n)$ is given by $\int_0^{r(\kappa_n)d} x f(x) dx$. When x is greater than $r_n d$ during the day, the CD distance is capped at $r_n d$, and this part of $D(\kappa_n)$ is given by $r_n d \int_{r(\kappa_n)d}^{\infty} f(x) dx$. The detailed explanation of the calculation of $D(\kappa_n)$, based on distribution $f(x)$, can be found in [25]. Clearly, it is assumed that the vehicle will operate in CD mode as much as possible before switching to CS mode. Although many PHEV products allow for users to switch between the two modes, the CD-first assumption is almost always assumed when assessing the potential for PHEV to reduce ownership cost or emissions. This assumption may need modification in places where electricity is expensive and gasoline is cheap.

The key innovation in this study is to use the evolving battery capacity κ_n that captures the battery degradation due to real-world operation instead of assuming the rated range r as always being available throughout the vehicle lifetime. Define κ_n as the battery capacity that is available to use at the beginning of day n , associated with κ_{n-1} . To consider the impact of battery degradation on range, the model from [27] is adopted to consider both the actual depth of discharge (DOD) and calendar aging, and modified into Equation (4) to align with the previous equation notations.

$$\kappa_n = \kappa_{n-1} - \kappa \cdot \left(B \left(\frac{D(\kappa_{n-1}) \cdot E(\kappa)}{\kappa_{n-1}} \right)^2 + K(\sqrt{24n} - \sqrt{24(n-1)}) \right) \quad (4)$$

where κ_n is the battery capacity at the beginning of day n and results from $n-1$ days of cycle and calendar aging, B is a fitting constant that equals battery degradation due to one complete charge–discharge cycle, and the calendar-based degradation coefficient K is a fitting constant where $K\sqrt{t} = K\sqrt{24n}$ describes calendar aging. The depth of discharge on day $n-1$ is represented by the ratio of electricity used during day $n-1$ to the total available battery capacity, i.e., $\frac{D(\kappa_{n-1}) \cdot E}{\kappa_{n-1}}$. The calendar aging effect of the day n is represented by $K(\sqrt{24n} - \sqrt{24(n-1)})$.

- Gasoline cost.

The 3rd component in Equation (1), gasoline cost, can be described in Equation (5) as a function of expected distance traveled in CS mode $S(r_n)$ on day n , the gasoline price P_g , the future-to-present discounting factor $P_f(n)$ and the gasoline consumption rate $G(r)$, which is a function of the battery capacity κ with three parameters, C_{S0} , C_{S1} and C_{S2} , as a bigger battery provides more opportunities to capture regenerative energy from braking. The function form assumes that the gasoline consumption rate starts at C_{S0} and reduces with the battery capacity down to the asymptote value $C_{S0} - C_{S1}$.

$$RC_g = \sum_{n=1}^N S(\kappa_n) \cdot G(\kappa) \cdot P_g \cdot P_f(n)$$

$$S(\kappa_n) = \int_0^\infty xf(x)dx - D(\kappa_n)$$

$$G(\kappa) = C_{S0} - C_{S1}(1 - e^{C_{S2} \cdot \kappa})$$
(5)

- Gasoline refueling cost.

The 4th component, RC_f , gasoline refueling behavior cost, represents the implicit cost, as opposed to the out-of-pocket explicit cost, of the refueling hassle (e.g., time and mental burden) in satisfying the gasoline refueling need. It is formulated in Equation (6) as a function of the expected distance traveled in CS mode $S(\kappa_n)$ on day n , the future-to-present discounting factor $P_f(n)$, and the gasoline consumption rate $G(r)$, the refueling behavior cost of one refueling trip C_{ref} and the average amount of gasoline refilled each refueling trip Q_{fillup} .

$$RC_f = \sum_{n=1}^N S(\kappa_n) \cdot G(\kappa) \cdot \frac{C_{ref}}{Q_{fillup}} \cdot P_f(n)$$
(6)

- Electricity recharging cost.

The 5th component, RC_c , electricity charging behavior cost, represents the implicit cost of the battery recharging hassle (e.g., time and mental burden) in satisfying the recharging demand. It is formulated in Equation (7) as a function of the expected CD distance $D(\kappa_n)$ on day n ; the future-to-present discounting factor $P_f(n)$; and the electricity consumption rate $E(r)$, the charging behavior cost of one recharging event C_{chg} and the maximum amount of electricity recharged during each event $\kappa_n (1 - P_{Cs})$. In reality, the electricity recharged per event may be less than $\kappa_n (1 - P_{Cs})$, resulting in a higher frequency of recharging and a higher charging behavior cost. Therefore, technically, RC_c should be interpreted as a perceived minimum behavior cost for electricity recharging, which is certainly relevant for consumer decision-making regarding the PHEV electric range.

$$RC_c = \sum_{n=1}^N D(\kappa_n) \cdot E(\kappa) \cdot \frac{C_{chg}}{\kappa_n (1 - P_{Cs})} \cdot P_f(n)$$
(7)

- Daily travel pattern.

For analysis of EV operation and energy use, the random daily travel distance x in Equation (3) has been commonly assumed to follow the Gamma distribution [25,26]. The Gamma distribution of daily distance was originally proposed by [28], validated by [26] and applied in several studies [9,25]. A Gamma distribution is traditionally described with the shape and scale parameters. These two parameters can determine and are determined by the mean and mode, denoted as M_n and M_d , respectively, of the random daily travel distance x . Because it is relatively easier to estimate M_n and M_d , the assumed Gamma probability density function of x is expressed as Equation (8), as used in Equations (3) and (5).

$$f(x) = \frac{x^{\frac{M_d}{M_n - M_d}} \cdot e^{\frac{-x}{M_n - M_d}}}{(M_n - M_d)^{\frac{M_n}{M_n - M_d}} \cdot \Gamma(\frac{M_n}{M_n - M_d})}$$
(8)

- Other considerations.

Battery degradation can be assumed to be negligible once the capacity reaches the CS mode threshold, i.e., when $\kappa_n = P_{CS} \cdot \kappa$ and $r(\kappa_n) = 0$, because at that point, the PHEV functions like an HEV, where the battery provides boosts and can charge through regenerative braking, but the net energy source is gasoline. Although in reality, the battery capacity in a HEV can continue to degrade, such degradation is only relevant in this study to the extent that it affects the vehicle fuel economy and fuel cost, which has been found to be only a 3% reduction after the vehicle has traveled a cumulative mileage of 150,000 miles [29]. Given the small effect, the battery capacity is assumed to be unchanging after it reaches the CS buffer capacity for model simplicity.

Microsoft Excel/VBA was used to compute all of the equations because of its ability to handle large amounts of data and use built in functions in conjunction with coded external macros. The equations were inputted into Excel/VBA to generate the total range cost. The Excel Solver was then used to find the initial battery capacity that would minimize the total range cost, given various starting parameters.

2.2. Base Case Data and Assumptions

The MOR-PHEV model with battery degradation, based on Equations (1)–(8), requires specifying 20 parameters. The values of these parameters for the base case are specified and explained in the order of the equations and summarized above in Table 2.

Table 2. Specification of base case parameter values.

Symbol	Unit	Value	Source or Justification
B	-	0.0001	0.0001 cycle-based coefficient [27], equivalent to a 2000-cycle life, representative of NMC batteries
C_0	-	0.8	assumed scaling factor for the power-law cost function
C_b	\$/kWh	250	calibrated pack cost at first 1 unit capacity, based on data from U.S. Department of Energy Vehicle Technologies Office [30]
C_{chg}	\$	3	assumption based on [31]
C_{E0}	kWh/km	0.31	similar to MY2023 Mitsubishi Outlander PHEV with 0.33 kWh/km electricity consumption rate for 20 kWh battery capacity
C_{E1}	kWh/km ²	0.001	0.001 kWh/km increase per additional 1 kWh battery capacity [24]
C_{ref}	\$	6.5	Power Payless survey study [32], U.S. Department of Transportation [33]
C_{S0}	L/km	0.0788	assumption of 30 MPG without battery buffer [34]
C_{S1}	L/km	-0.0315	so that the asymptote value is 50 MPG [34]
C_{S2}	1/kWh	-0.3	asymptote rate assumption
d	-	100%	based on nightly recharge assumption
K	hr ^{-0.5}	0.0005	0.0005 h ^{-0.5} as calendar-based degradation coefficient [27]
M_n	km	60.2	average daily driving distance
M_d	km	51.2	typical daily commute round-trip distance
N	-	3650	based on 10 years of vehicle lifetime
P_{CS}	-	25%	based on the 20–30% SOC window in typical PHEV products
P_e	\$/kWh	0.175	U.S. national average electricity price in July 2025 for residential use [35]
P_g	\$/L	0.872	U.S. Energy Information Administration [36]
Q_{fillup}	L	37.85	assumption based on [9]
R	-	2%	the 2023 OMB's Circular A-4 [37]

For Equation (2), the battery unit cost at 1 kWh (C_b) is calibrated to be \$250/kWh, based on the assumed $C_0 = 0.8$ scaling factor and the (unit cost, capacity) data points of (\$128/kWh, 30kWh) and (\$150/kWh, 10kWh). These data points are aligned with the battery cost assessments by the U.S. Department of Energy at \$128–133/kWh in 2025. This is a conservative and appropriate assumption for the base case. Also, it has been reported

that the global average has reached \$108/kWh, China's average has reached \$84/kWh, and North America and Europe's average has reached about 44% and 56% higher than the China average, largely due to trade barriers and local inflation [38]. The same reports projects a global average of \$70–80/kWh by 2030 [38]. These estimates are more optimistic than the base case assumptions. Given the variations in estimates and expected technology improvement, a pack cost multiplier will be applied to RC_b in sensitivity and alternative scenario analysis later.

For Equation (3), the price of electricity (P_e) is assumed to be \$0.175/kWh, based on the U.S. national average electricity price in July 2025 for residential use [35]. It is worth noting that the residential electricity price in the US is significantly lower than the price in Europe (roughly half) and higher than the price in China (roughly double), which is relevant for understanding the market dynamics of EV adoption. Electricity prices in the US have been steadily increasing over the past decade and are expected to continue rising.

Assuming a 10-year vehicle lifetime, the corresponding total number of days (N) is 3650. We ignore the variation in vehicle lifetime in the real world and the complication of battery or vehicle residual value for the optimization. The residual value effect is mostly discounted over 10 years and, if desired, can theoretically be equivalently captured by sensitivity analysis on the battery pack cost. Therefore, the 10-year lifetime simplification is appropriate.

The fixed (C_{E0}) and variable coefficients for the electricity consumption rate (E) are assumed to be 0.31 kWh/km and 0.001 kWh/km², respectively. This is derived based on the assumption of a 0.001 kWh/km increase per additional 1 kWh battery capacity, based on [24], and a 0.33 kWh/km electricity consumption rate for 20 kWh battery capacity, similar to a MY2023 Mitsubishi Outlander PHEV. The range extension ratio (d) is assumed to be 100%, which means one full recharge during the nighttime, although multiple within-day recharges will be analyzed in alternative scenarios. For users who do not plug in each night, their behavior can be reflected by a smaller d (i.e., $d < 100%$). For users who plug in every night and also recharge the PHEV at work or occasionally in public places, their PHEV usage can be characterized by a larger d , such as $d = 150%$, which translates the diligent nightly charging and within-day charging into a battery capacity that is 1.5 times higher than the rated capacity. Despite the above flexibility in MOR-PHEV, we recognize that the nightly charging assumption may be more optimistic than what is observed in the current PHEV usage data. Considering the real-world PHEV designs that usually leave 20–30% of the total battery capacity as the buffer capacity for CS operation, we assume 25% in the base case as the percentage of the battery capacity reserved for the hybrid or CS model operation (P_{CS}). The annual discount rate is assumed to be 2%, according to the guidance in the 2023 OMB's Circular A-4 [37].

For Equation (4), based on the study [27], the calendar-based degradation coefficient (K) is assumed to be 0.0005 h^{-0.5}, which corresponds to a calendar-based degradation to 80% in 18 years or to 85% in 10 years (the calendar-based degradation slows down in later years). The cycle-based degradation coefficient (B), i.e., the battery degradation due to one complete charge–discharge cycle, is assumed to be 0.0001, which is equivalent to a 2000-cycle life before the 80% state of health “knee point”, which is representative of current nickel manganese cobalt (NMC) batteries. Note that B is lower for lithium iron phosphate (LFP) batteries, which can last 3000–6000 cycles. The real-world degradation depends on the charge–discharge SOC window. In general, a deep charge–discharge cycle, such as between 20% and 80%, leads to greater degradation than multiple shallower cycles that together have the same cumulative depth, such as 2 cycles that are each between 30% and 60%. Such a degradation “scale diseconomy” mechanism is well recognized and is reflected by the power function form in Equation (4). An ambient temperature also affects the speed of degradation [39,40]. In summary, the base case value of $B = 0.0001$

represents NMC batteries operating at room temperature, should decrease for LFP batteries or in the case of technology improvement, and should increase in the case of extreme ambient temperature.

For Equation (5), the gasoline price (P_g) is assumed to be \$3.3/gallon or \$0.87/L, based on fuel price information from the U.S. Energy Information Administration [36]. Based on [34], the gasoline consumption rate in CS mode is assumed to be 0.0788 L/km (or 30 MPG) with zero battery buffer (i.e., no hybrid operation, no regenerative braking) (C_{S0}). The gasoline consumption rate gradually reduces at the $-0.3/\text{kWh}$ asymptote rate (C_{S2}) and approaches the asymptote value of 0.0474 L/km ($C_{S0} - C_{S1}$) (or 50 MPG). Although fuel prices often fluctuate, the gasoline price in the US is among the lowest for major economies: 25–30% lower than the price in China and 50–60% lower than the price in Europe.

For Equation (6), according to the Power Payless survey study [32], Americans on average spend 20 min for each gas station visit. The hourly rate is assumed to be \$26/hour and 75% of the hourly rate is assumed to estimate the travel time value, based on the 2016 Revised Value of Travel Time Guidance by the U.S. Department of Transportation [33]. Therefore, the refueling behavior cost of one refueling trip (C_{ref}) is assumed to be $\left(\frac{20}{60}\right) \cdot 26 \cdot 75\% = \6.5 . The amount of gasoline to be refilled each refueling trip is assumed to be 37.85 L or 10 gallons, based on the assumption of a 15 gallon tank size for a typical PHEV vehicle and the finding that on average, one-third of a tank of fuel remains when drivers stop for gas [41].

For Equation (7), the charging behavior cost of one recharging event (C_{chg}) is assumed to be \$3 per recharge event, similarly to [9]. This can vary based on income, housing type and daily driving habits. Note that this is used to characterize the charging behavior cost of charging events.

For Equation (8), the average number of miles driven per year in the U.S. is assumed to be 13,662 miles or 21,987 km, according to the data from the Federal Highway Administration. This leads to an average daily distance of 60.2 km (M_n). According to the U.S. Department of Transportation and the Bureau of Transportation Statistics, the average round-trip commuting distance is approximately 31.8 miles or 51.2 km, which is assumed as the mode of daily distance (M_d). Note that such assumptions capture a static average driving behavior, which may need to be altered in future research to reflect changes in lifestyle, infrastructure improvement or household composition.

3. Results

3.1. Base Case and Optimization Significance

In the base case, defined by the MOR-PHEV model of Equations (1)–(8) and the parameter assumptions in Table 2—the total range-related cost (RC_{total}), battery cost (RC_b), electricity cost (RC_e), gasoline cost (RC_g), gasoline refueling behavior cost (RC_f) and charging behavior cost (RC_c), as corresponding to the cost components in Equation (1)—are calculated based on Equations (2)–(8) and shown in Figure 1. The optimal battery capacity is found to be 47.43 kWh, which includes 35.6 kWh of CD capacity that results in a 99.5 km electric range. The minimized total range-related cost, RC_{total} as in Equation (1), is \$20,192, consisting of \$5491 battery cost (27%), \$8736 electricity cost (43%), \$460 gasoline cost (2%), \$340 gasoline refueling behavior cost (2%), and \$5164 charging behavior cost (26%). As analyzed by [9], the optimal battery capacity is determined by a balance of the first-order derivatives of the five cost components (i.e., the slopes of the five curves in Figure 1).

Figure 1. MOR-PHEV base case—cost components as a function of feasible battery capacity.

The MOR-PHEV minimization model is not strictly convex, based on the RC_{total} curve in Figure 1. The discreteness point at (4.6 kWh, \$25,430) and the steep increase between 4 kWh and 4.6 kWh are caused by the complete degradation of the battery CD capacity. The battery capacity for CS operation is assumed to be 25% or 3.8 kWh, whichever is larger. When the battery is small enough (such as below 4.6 kWh) and the cycle-based degradation coefficient is large enough (0.01% in the base case), the CD capacity completely wears out just at the end of the assumed 10-year life. Before such a maximum-cost point as in Figure 1, the total range-related cost (RC_{total}) decreases quickly with an even smaller battery. This is because with a small battery, the charging behavior cost has become a major burden, as shown by the RC_c curve in Figure 1, due to the CD-first and nightly charging assumptions (i.e., users are not allowed to skip charging the small batteries in the model, even though charge skipping is very likely in the real world due to the small electric-driving gain and large charging behavior cost). If the battery can be smaller than the discreteness point, complete degradation of the CD capacity can occur even earlier than the 10-year life, and the high charging behavior cost can be avoided. That is, when the battery is as small as 4.6 kWh in the base case, the optimization would rather choose an even smaller battery so that the PHEV can turn into a HEV sooner. Fortunately, in reality, we are mostly interested in battery capacity that is large enough to maintain certain CD capacity throughout the vehicle life. As shown in Figure 1, with a reasonable lower-bound constraint (set to 5 kWh in scenario results later) for the battery capacity, the objective function would become practically convex and easy to minimize.

Such practical convexity is mainly shaped by the evolution of the five cost components with battery capacity. As shown in Figure 1, the rapid reduction in gasoline cost and refueling behavior cost with battery capacity in the small capacity interval (e.g., [5kWh 40kWh]) are the most influential on the total range-related cost. This also means that in

the small capacity interval, the marginal benefit of reducing the gasoline cost and refueling behavior cost outweighs the marginal increase in battery cost and electricity cost. Battery cost increase is the main driver of the rebound of the total range-related cost in the large capacity interval (e.g., [50kWh 80kWh]).

The optimization is meaningful, as illustrated by the magnitude of total range-related cost difference, \$5238, between the optimal value and the worst or highest value. In terms of the tangible cost on the consumer, between a misguided maximum of 90 kWh and the optimal 47.43 kWh in the base case, the difference in battery cost is as large as \$3512: a significant amount of possible out-of-pocket loss without optimization.

As previously mentioned and emphasized here, the MOR-PHEV model is an optimization model to generate useful insights instead of prescribing direct recommendations. For that purpose, some assumptions may be unrealistic but relevant. For example, the above finding of non-convexity is due to the assumption that the CD capacity is always used before the vehicle operating in CS mode. In reality, this may not be true, as the driver may switch to CS mode before depleting the CD capacity, or skip charging and use the vehicle as a regular hybrid vehicle, as is often observed. However, the above non-convexity finding points to the need to understand the minimum CD capacity that justifies the burden of recharging, as also pointed out by [42]. That also explains and supports the industry trend of increasing the PHEV CD range over the past decade, as charging infrastructure development still falls behind the level needed to make the behavior of diligent nightly charging common. Also, when a large cycle-based degradation coefficient is combined with inconvenient charging conditions, under the CD-first and nightly charging assumptions, PHEVs with small batteries will face high charging behavior costs and lose ground to either HEVs or PHEVs with large batteries. In reality, users of PHEVs with small batteries and without convenient charging conditions have been observed to skip charging and operate them largely as HEVs, but the useful insights here are that manufacturers can aim their large-battery PHEVs at those who can afford them and small-battery PHEVs at those who can easily access chargers, especially those wireless or intelligent charging technologies that cut charging behavior costs to almost zero. Also, manufacturers should protect or improve battery health through innovative battery chemistry or thermal management systems after understanding the value of slowing down degradation, which will be quantified later in 3.5.

3.2. Sensitivity Analysis

The optimization, in terms of both the minimized total range-related cost (RC_{total}^*) and the optimal battery capacity (κ^*), is overall robust against all 13 exogenous parameters in Equations (1)–(8). As shown in Figure 2, a $\pm 20\%$ change in any of the parameters results in less than 20% change in $|RC_{total}^*|$ or $|\kappa^*|$. The change direction of either dependent variable is logical. For example, a 20% increase in electricity price leads to a 6.9% reduction in κ^* and a 8.5% increase in RC_{total}^* . The most influential parameters are the annual distance, gasoline consumption rate, battery unit cost, charging behavior cost, electricity price and gasoline price. The sensitivities of RC_{total}^* and κ^* to a given parameter are mostly correlated. Exceptions are the gasoline consumption rate, gasoline price, refueling behavior cost and gasoline refuel amount, all of which impact κ^* greater than RC_{total}^* .

Figure 2. Sensitivity of minimized total range-related cost and optimal battery capacity.

The sensitivity analysis in Figure 2 is based on a simple but common method of a $\pm 20\%$ change in any of the parameters. This approach provides a quick assessment of parameter sensitivity and ignores the difference in costs, difficulty or likelihood of the $\pm 20\%$ change in practice, therefore calling for the results to be interpreted carefully. Although expanding the sensitivity analysis to consider such practical sensitivity in all the parameters is difficult and beyond the scope of this study, it is worth pointing out that the degradation coefficients may vary easily beyond the $\pm 20\%$ range. For example, from an NMC battery with a 2000-cycle life to an LFP battery with 6000-cycle life, the cycle-based degradation coefficient can decrease by 67%. Extreme high or low temperatures can permanently or temporarily reduce the battery capacity. However, battery thermal management systems can usually ensure that the battery operates within a desirable temperature window.

It is also recognized that the sensitivity analysis does not consider the structural robustness of the model in Equations (1)–(8). For example, the same study upon which we base the assumption of a linear relationship between the electricity consumption rate and battery capacity also discusses power-law function forms [24], which may affect our results. The Gamma distribution for daily travel distance has been validated as being sufficiently accurate for PHEV energy analysis, but alternative function forms such as Weibull or Lognormal distributions have also been adopted [26]. Qualitatively, for the same annual distance, the probability density function that skews toward a larger proportion of long daily distance and thus more deep charge–discharge cycles can lead to faster battery degradation. Similar meaningful hypotheses can be raised around many other functional forms for the parameters and require separate studies in future research.

3.3. Interactive Effect of Degradation and Annual Distance

Based on the above results, we further studied the interactive effect on RC_{total}^* and κ^* of degradation and one of these factors: annual distance, gasoline consumption rate, battery unit cost, or charging behavior cost. The purpose is to reveal whether the optimal-range impact of degradation performance, represented by the cycle-based degradation coefficient, varies with other influential factors. The range of the cycle-based degradation coefficient is assumed to vary between 0.01% and 0.05% [43].

The first interactive term, driving intensity, is studied to understand how and why the optimal battery capacity changes with battery degradation performance under different levels of driving intensity. In the base case, the annual average daily driving distance and typical daily commute round-trip distance are assumed to be 60.2 km and 51.2 km, which are used to specify the daily distance Gamma distribution. The driving intensity multiplier, ranging from 0.6 to 1.4, is multiplied with the daily distance in the base case. For each value of driving intensity multiplier, the cycle-based degradation coefficient is assumed to vary between 0.01% and 0.05%. MOR-PHEV is used to optimize the initial battery capacity κ by minimizing the total range-related cost RC_{total} for each combination of cycle-based degradation coefficient and driving intensity multiplier, with all other parameters staying at the base case values.

As shown in Figure 3, before the combination enters the “high driving intensity + fast degradation” zone, for a given level of driving intensity, the optimal initial battery capacity κ^* typically increases with the cycle-based degradation coefficient. This is because with faster degradation, a bigger battery is needed to compensate the lost capacity during the vehicle lifetime and provide enough capacity to deliver the electrification benefits for that driving intensity.

At the 0.01% cycle-based degradation coefficient, the optimal initial battery capacity κ^* initially increases with the driving intensity. This suggests that high driving intensity justifies paying more for a bigger battery to save on the charging behavior cost and gasoline cost.

But when driving intensity is high, or when the cycle-based degradation coefficient is high, the optimal initial battery capacity κ^* can drop significantly. This is because the high driving intensity will result in more frequent deep discharging and deep charging, which can work with a high cycle-based degradation coefficient and accelerate the battery degradation. At some point, the consumer would rather choose a small battery, let it quickly degrade to the CS buffer capacity and permanently switch to CS hybrid driving without frequent charging inconvenience.

The minimized total range-related cost is overall stable against the cycle-based degradation coefficient for a given driving intensity, and expectedly increases with driving intensity for a given cycle-based degradation coefficient.

Figure 3. Interactive effect of driving intensity and cycle-based degradation speed.

3.4. Interactive Effect of Degradation and CS Fuel Economy

CS fuel economy, measured by the miles per gallon of gasoline (MPG) after the battery is depleted, is studied to understand how and why the optimal battery capacity changes with battery degradation performance under different levels of CS fuel economy. In the base case, the CS fuel economy is assumed to be 30 MPG. In the following interaction analysis, the CS fuel economy is assumed to vary from 18 to 43 MPG. Similarly, the cycle-based degradation coefficient is assumed to vary between 0.01% and 0.05%. MOR-PHEV is used to optimize the initial battery capacity κ^* by minimizing the total range-related cost RC_{total}^* , for each combination of cycle-based degradation coefficient and CS fuel economy, with all other parameters staying at the base case values.

As shown in Figure 4, before the combination enters the “high CS fuel economy + fast degradation” zone, for a given CS fuel economy, the optimal initial battery capacity κ^* typically increases with the cycle-based degradation coefficient, for the same reason of extra capacity compensating for degradation, as previously explained.

Starting from 18 MPG, for each given cycle-based degradation coefficient, the optimal initial battery capacity κ^* generally decreases with the CS fuel economy. This is because a higher efficiency during the CS mode makes the marginal electrification benefit of the battery capacity less appealing. Why does a consumer want additional battery capacity if the vehicle is sufficiently efficient on gasoline? In other words, a low CS fuel economy motivates consumers to choose a bigger battery for the PHEV.

But when the CS fuel economy is sufficiently high, or when the cycle-based degradation coefficient is high, the optimal initial battery capacity κ^* can drop significantly. This is because the high CS fuel economy will make the electrification benefit less appealing (e.g., low fuel cost on electricity) and the electrification disbenefit (e.g., charging behavior cost) more annoying. At some point, the consumer would rather choose a small battery, allow CD mode to become unusable (due to the fast cycle-based degradation) and rely solely on the highly efficient CS hybrid driving without frequent recharging inconvenience.

The minimized total range-related cost increases with the cycle-based degradation coefficient, but it deviates and stabilizes with the combination of “high CS fuel economy + fast degradation”. This also explains the sharp drop of the optimal initial battery capacity κ^* on the left figure. That is, with a high CS fuel economy, a small battery allows for the consumer to “make use of” the fast degradation and prevent the further increase in the total range-related cost.

Figure 4. Interactive effect of charge-sustaining fuel economy and cycle-based degradation speed.

3.5. Interactive Effect of Degradation and Battery Unit Cost

Battery unit cost, measured by USD per kWh of the initial battery capacity, is studied to understand how and why the optimal battery capacity changes with battery degradation performance under different battery unit costs. In the base case, the battery unit cost is assumed to be \$128/kWh at 30 kWh with a scaling factor of 0.8. In the following interaction analysis, the battery unit cost is assumed to vary from 1.0 to 0.5, representing up to 50% cost reduction. Similarly, the cycle-based degradation coefficient is assumed to vary between 0.01% and 0.05%. MOR-PHEV is used to optimize the initial battery capacity κ^* by minimizing the total range-related cost RC_{total}^* for each combination of cycle-based degradation coefficient and battery unit cost, with all other parameters staying at the base case values.

Unlike the previous discussions, we do not observe disruptive interaction effects between the cycle-based degradation coefficient and battery unit cost on κ^* . As shown in Figure 5, both κ^* and RC_{total}^* increase with the cycle-based degradation coefficient for a given battery unit cost. A faster cycle-based degradation motivates consumers to choose a bigger battery, in order to compensate for the loss of battery capacity and electrification benefits. With everything else being equal, this logically leads to a higher battery cost, which is more than the increase in electrification benefit, and thus a higher total range-related cost, RC_{total}^* .

For the same cycle-based degradation coefficient, a smaller battery unit cost results in κ^* and RC_{total}^* changing in opposite directions. As seen in Figure 5, lower battery costs

make the incremental increase in battery capacity more worthwhile, i.e., generating more electrification benefit than the added battery cost. But overall, the electrification benefit induced by a bigger battery outweighs the increased battery pack cost, resulting in a decrease in the total range-related cost, RC_{total}^* .

Figure 5. Interactive effect of battery unit cost and cycle-based degradation speed.

The interaction analysis of degradation and battery cost also reveals some important quantitative information regarding the value of reducing the cycle-based degradation coefficient. As shown on the left graph of Figure 5, the improvement of the cycle-based degradation coefficient from 0.05% to 0.01% reduces the optimal battery capacity by 19.5–20.6 kWh or 4.9–5.2 kWh per one basis point (0.01%) reduction in the cycle-based degradation coefficient, depending on the battery unit cost. This shows the significant benefit of battery durability improvement in reducing the demand for battery capacity and the associated critical minerals and lifecycle emissions.

On the right graph of Figure 5, the cycle-based degradation coefficient from 0.05% to 0.01% reduces the total range-related cost by \$1100–1989 or \$275–497 per one basis point (0.01%) reduction in the cycle-based degradation coefficient, depending on the battery unit cost. This is the value generated by the cycle-based degradation improvement and also appears to be significant. Note that this value is for one vehicle and should be multiplied by the number of vehicles for estimating the total market value of such a battery health improvement.

4. Conclusions

Optimizing the electric driving range or the battery capacity of PHEVs is relevant to their vehicle design, consumer ownership value, lifecycle environmental impact and critical material demand, and thus can affect the role of PHEVs in electrifying and decarbonizing transportation. PHEV range optimization has been carried out from different angles but faces important knowledge gaps, such as consideration of battery degradation. This study expands the existing MOR-PHEV model to consider the cycle-based and calendar-

based battery degradation mechanisms, in addition to driving intensity, battery unit cost, charging availability, etc.

Like most optimization studies, this study is normative, especially due to the inclusion and exclusion of cost components and the assumptions regarding costs and technology attributes. Such normative optimization is not intended to predict actual future decisions by consumers, but to provide (1) empirical insights if a decision-making reader sufficiently agrees on the logic and assumptions of the study; or (2) a modeling framework for decision-making readers to insert their own assumptions or expand structural components or both, to generate their own normative insights.

One limitation of the study is that the optimized range or optimized battery capacity results are neither a prediction of future choices by consumers or manufacturers, nor a prescription of what ought to be purchased or produced. However, such optimal results and their logical linkage to the underlying factors provide valuable insights and reference to real-world decision-making, where consumers, producers or policy makers consider such rationality-based optimal results in addition to beyond-model factors in the real-world political and macroeconomic context. Another limitation is the static parameter assumptions behind each result, such as electricity price, battery unit cost, nightly charging, CD-first operation, etc. Particularly, although the ambient temperature may vary significantly, the operating temperature of the battery is assumed to stay within the desirable range, based on the popularity of the battery thermal management system. Values of the base case parameters are based on real-world data but do not fully reflect their variation or heterogeneity. Some assumptions, such as nightly charging and CD-first operation, may be more optimistic than the current usage reality and may be more conservative than what future charging infrastructure could enable. Analysis of parameter sensitivity and alternative scenarios was conducted in this study to reveal the effect of the dynamics to some extent, but further research is needed to incorporate such a range optimization framework with consumer choice or energy system models in order to capture the effect of system dynamics and feedback.

This study results in three key findings. First, the optimization is found to be significant, possibly reducing battery cost for consumers by \$3000–5000. The magnitude of the optimization value is comparable to the expired U.S. EV tax credit of up to \$7500 or China's early market EV purchase subsidy of up to \$9000. The optimal results, in terms of the minimized total cost and the optimized battery capacity, are robust against all exogenous parameters, based on sensitivity analysis against all 13 parameters. The three most influential factors, annual driving distance, CS gasoline consumption rate and battery unit cost, are identified for further analysis of the effects of their interactions with battery degradation.

Second, based on the interaction effect analysis in 3.3 and 3.4, high driving intensity and high CS efficiency can lead to optimization tipping points at faster cycle-based degradation, where the degradation effect is so significant that the consumer is better off by choosing a small-battery PHEV (or HEV if the choice space expands beyond PHEV) in order to fully degrade the battery faster, totally avoid the charging behavior cost earlier, and maximally benefit from the high CS efficiency earlier. The implication is that for PHEV products to successfully compete against non-plug-in hybrid vehicles in serving high-driving-intensity consumers, the battery must be durable, the charging must be convenient, or both. In other words, if the manufacture (1) aims at high-driving-intensity consumers who do not have convenient access to chargers; (2) is not competitive in battery durability; and (3) is competitive in engine and vehicle overall efficiency, then focusing on a non-plug-in hybrid may be less risky than PHEVs. For R&D and policy decision makers, this points to the importance of reducing cycle-based degradation through continued

battery R&D and the importance of improving vehicle efficiency and embracing non-plug-in hybrids as cost-effective alternatives for certain frequent drivers.

Third, based on the interaction effect analysis in 3.5, one basis point (0.01%) reduction in the cycle-based degradation coefficient reduces the optimal battery capacity by 4.9–5.2 kWh and increases the consumer value by \$275–497, depending on the battery unit cost. These are useful insights for decision-making regarding battery technology R&D, battery chemistry roadmaps, critical material supply risks, and EV product strategies.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

BEV	battery electric vehicle
CD	charge-depleting
CO ₂	carbon dioxide
CS	charge-sustaining
DOD	depth of discharge
EV	electric vehicle
GHG	greenhouse gas
MOR-PHEV	market-oriented optimal range for PHEV
MPG	miles per gallon
PHEV	plug-in hybrid electric vehicle

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